

Impact of Transfer Pricing Audits on Revenue Collection Efficiency in Tanzania's Large Taxpayer Department

Pascal Gomba

Department of Academic Research and Consultancy, Institute of Tax Administration, Tanzania

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
22 April 2025

ABSTRACT

Transfer pricing posed significant risks to domestic revenue mobilization, especially in developing countries like Tanzania, where large taxpayers dominated the fiscal landscape. In response to growing concerns over base erosion and profit shifting by multinational enterprises, the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA) introduced the Transfer Pricing Regulations in 2018 to enhance compliance and improve revenue outcomes. This study evaluated the impact of these regulatory audits on tax revenue collection efficiency, particularly focused on total tax revenue and corporate income tax between 2015/16 and 2022/23.

Using a time-series quantitative research design, the study analysed secondary data on revenue collections which were obtained from TRA archives, Statistical analysis involved regression modelling using STATA 17, complemented by Microsoft Excel for data visualization. The regression results shown a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) increased in both total tax revenue and corporate income tax collections following the implementation of transfer pricing audits. On average, post-2018 revenues increased by TZS 4.77 trillion for total tax and TZS 1.69 trillion for corporate income tax, with adjusted R^2 values of 0.633 and 0.682 respectively. These findings highlighted the fiscal importance of targeted audits in improving tax administration effectiveness.

The study concluded that transfer pricing audits had a positive and measurable effect on revenue performance in Tanzania. However, sustainable gains required continuous investment in audit capacity, inter-agency coordination, and digital innovations. It recommended strengthening the regulatory framework, increasing technical training for auditors, and enhancing data-sharing mechanisms to ensure long-term compliance and revenue growth.

Corresponding Author:
Pascal Gomba

KEYWORDS: Transfer pricing; Revenue collection; Audit effectiveness; Tax enforcement; Large Taxpayers; Tanzania

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Taxation plays a pivotal role in the socio-economic development of any country, serving as the primary vehicle for financing public services such as infrastructure, healthcare, and education. In Tanzania, tax revenue accounts for a significant proportion of government financing, underpinning national development plans and reducing reliance on external aid (Bhattachargee & Baid, 2018). The integrity and efficiency of the tax system, therefore, are not merely administrative concerns they are foundational to fiscal sustainability and good governance. However, persistent challenges in tax administration, particularly in addressing non-compliance among large taxpayers, continue to undermine revenue mobilization efforts.

A major area of concern has been the tax behavior of multinational enterprises (MNEs), which often exploit loopholes in international taxation through profit shifting and

base erosion techniques such as transfer pricing. Transfer pricing involves the pricing of transactions between related parties within the same corporate group, and if manipulated, it can result in significant loss of taxable income for high-tax jurisdictions like Tanzania (OECD, 2013; Beebeejaun, 2018). These practices create a compliance gap that directly threatens the country's ability to meet its domestic financing objectives.

In response, the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA) introduced Transfer Pricing Regulations in 2018, establishing robust documentation requirements and empowering tax auditors to scrutinize related-party transactions. The implementation of these regulations is aligned with the OECD's arm's length principle and reflects Tanzania's commitment to international best practices in combating tax avoidance (TRA, 2020; United Nations, 2011). The regulations also aim to increase transparency and deter abuse

through targeted transfer pricing audits a measure that functions not only as a deterrent but also as a proactive revenue mobilization mechanism.

The impact of tax audits, particularly transfer pricing audits, has attracted considerable scholarly attention in recent years. Empirical studies suggest that while audits can significantly enhance compliance in the short run, their effect on actual revenue collection is less frequently quantified especially in Sub-Saharan African contexts (Advani, Elming & Shaw, 2021; Alm, Jackson & McKee, 2009). Research by Agosto et al. (2017) and Kasper and Alm (2020) emphasizes that the effectiveness of audits is contingent on the credibility of enforcement, audit frequency, and the perceived fairness of the tax system. In addition, Ebrahim et al. (2021) note that institutional capacity, legal clarity, and audit selectivity are key drivers of successful enforcement outcomes in low-income countries.

While previous studies in Tanzania (Chalu & Mzee, 2018; Chatama, 2013) have examined the determinants of tax audit effectiveness and the role of ICT in audit processes, there remains a gap in evaluating the direct revenue impact of transfer pricing audits since their formal adoption in 2018. This study seeks to fill that gap by assessing how these audits have influenced total tax revenue and corporate income tax collections in the Large Taxpayer Department. The TRA's large taxpayer segment, comprising more than 400 entities, accounts for nearly 70% of the nation’s revenue base making the efficiency of its audit mechanisms critically important.

By applying a time-series regression approach using data from 2015/16 to 2022/23, this study not only contributes empirical evidence on the fiscal yield of transfer pricing audits but also examines operational challenges that may affect their effectiveness. These include delays in legal resolutions, capacity limitations, and the evolving sophistication of MNE tax planning strategies (Lohse & Riedel, 2012; Melnychenko et al., 2017). Ultimately, the research seeks to provide practical insights for tax policymakers, auditors, and international stakeholders interested in strengthening revenue administration and ensuring that large corporations contribute fairly to the national tax base.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Research Design

A time-series quantitative research design was adopted to examine the effect of transfer pricing audits on revenue collections in Tanzania. The study focused on macro-level revenue trends from 2015/16 to 2022/23, covering periods

before and after the introduction of the 2018 Transfer Pricing Regulations. Regression and trend analyses were used to estimate the causal impact of transfer pricing audits on total tax revenue and corporate income tax.

2.2 Sampling and Data Collection Method

Data from this study considered 9 fiscal years of utilizing secondary data on total tax revenue and corporate income tax collections were extracted from TRA archives for the years 2015/16 to 2022/23. Primary data were obtained via questionnaires administered to senior auditors involved in transfer pricing enforcement. The questionnaire included revenue-related outcomes and perceived audit effectiveness.

2.3 Data Analysis

Data were cleaned using Microsoft Excel software package from Microsoft office package of version 2019 then the inferential computation of estimating the Regression analysis was conducted using STATA version 17 to test the significance of transfer pricing audit introduction on revenue. Further Excel package of Microsoft was utilized to visualize these findings with line graphs, aiding in the interpretation of trends over time.

A dummy variable D_t was created to represent the pre-audit and post-audit years (0 = before 2018, 1 = after 2018). The dependent variables were:

TR_t : Total Tax Revenue in year t

CIT_t : Corporate Income Tax in year t

The Pooled OLS regression models estimated were as shown in equation 1 and 2.

$$TR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 D_t + \epsilon_t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$CIT_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 D_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Whereby β_1, α_1 represent the marginal effect of transfer pricing audits on revenue and ϵ_t, μ_t are the error terms

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 Revenue Trend Analysis (2015/16–2022/23)

As shown in Table 1, Tanzania’s total tax revenue from large taxpayers has steadily increased from TZS 9.5 trillion in 2015/16 to TZS 17.2 trillion in 2022/23. This trend implies improved collection efficiency, which coincides with the introduction of the 2018 Transfer Pricing Regulations as shown on figure 1. Though the growth cannot be solely attributed to audits, the consistent upward trajectory supports the argument that regulatory tightening may be positively influencing revenue outcomes.

Table 1: Trend of Total Tax Revenue Collections (in Trillion TZS)

Fiscal Year	Total Tax Revenue
2015/16	9.5
2016/17	10.2
2017/18	10.8
2018/19	12.0

Fiscal Year	Total Tax Revenue
2019/20	13.5
2020/21	15.4
2021/22	16.6
2022/23	17.2

Figure 1: Trend of total tax revenues collections (in Trillion TZS)

Similarly, corporate income tax collections on table 2 rose from TZS 1.9 trillion to TZS 4.6 trillion over the interval of 9 fiscal year period. This reinforces the notion that enhanced scrutiny on intra-group pricing practices especially those

aimed at profit shifting has positively impacted revenue mobilization as shown in figure 2. The impact is more noticeable from 2018 onward, implying a possible correlation with audit initiation.

Table 2: Trend of Corporate Income Tax Collections (in Trillion TZS)

Fiscal Year	Corporate Income Tax
2015/16	1.9
2016/17	2.1
2017/18	2.4
2018/19	2.9
2019/20	3.4
2020/21	3.9
2021/22	4.3
2022/23	4.6

Figure 2: Trend of Corporate Income Tax Collections (in Trillion TZS)

3.2 Description of comparison based on differences

Figure 4.3 below presents a graphical analysis result of the trend of tax revenue collections over the years. Prior to 2018, there was a gentle fluctuation in the revenue collections. However, the trend changed after 2018, especially beginning from 2019, where the sharp growth of large taxpayer revenue

collections is recorded, even though with fluctuations. In general, the line trend, confirm the regression results, of a positive effect of establishment of transfer pricing audit on tax revenue collections. The persisting downward fluctuations are reasons for the lack of statistical significance (statistical stability) of the effect on tax revenues

Figure 3: Trend of Tax Revenue Collections 2015-2018 & 2019 – 2022

3.3 Model estimation

3.3.1 Impact of policy on Total tax revenue

The regression model on table 3 analyzing total tax revenue indicates that the baseline average total tax revenue before the 2018 introduction of transfer pricing audits was approximately TZS 5.23 trillion, as shown by the constant

value. The coefficient for the Year Dummy variable is 4.77, which suggests that post-2018, the policy implementation was associated with a TZS 4.77 trillion increase in average annual total tax revenue.

This result is statistically significant, evidenced by a t-value of 10.53 and a p-value of 0.009, indicating that the observed change is highly unlikely to have occurred by chance. The

relatively low standard error (0.4525) reinforces the reliability of this estimate. The model’s Adjusted R² value of 0.633 signifies that approximately 63.3% of the variation in

total tax revenue across the observed period is explained by the model.

Table 3: Regression Results – Total Tax Revenue

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Constant	5.233	0.357	14.63	0.003
Year Dummy	4.766	0.452	10.53	0.009
Adjusted R²	0.633			

3.3.2 Impact of policy on Corporate Income Tax

For corporate income tax on table 4, the regression results reveal a pre-policy baseline revenue of TZS 2.13 trillion, as indicated by the constant value. The Year Dummy coefficient is 1.69, suggesting that the introduction of transfer pricing audits led to an average annual increase of TZS 1.69 trillion in corporate income tax.

This result is also statistically significant, supported by a t-value of 4.01 and a p-value of 0.007, with a standard error of 0.4211, reflecting consistent estimation. The Adjusted R² value of 0.682 means that 68.2% of the variance in corporate tax collections is accounted for by the model, pointing to a robust relationship between the audit policy and tax revenue performance.

Table 4: Regression Results Corporate Income Tax

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Constant	2.133	0.333	6.41	0.000
Year Dummy	1.686	0.421	4.01	0.007
Adjusted R²	0.682			

4.0 DISCUSSION

The findings of this study confirmed that the introduction of transfer pricing audits in Tanzania in 2018 significantly impacted tax revenue performance. Regression results show that total tax revenue rose by an average of TZS 4.77 trillion annually post-implementation, while corporate income tax increased by TZS 1.69 trillion. These results are statistically significant and strongly support the argument that regulatory enforcement through audits yields substantial fiscal benefits. Based on the results there is an upward trajectory in revenue aligns with international evidence from countries such as Italy and the UK, where audits were shown to drive long-term improvements in collection (Advani et al., 2021; Agosto et al., 2017). The policy acted as both a detection mechanism and a signal to corporations that aggressive tax planning would no longer be tolerated, leading to more accurate declarations of income, particularly in complex financing arrangements.

The stronger effect observed on corporate income tax compared to total revenue suggests that audits particularly influenced behaviours related to profit shifting and intra-group financial transactions common tactics used by multinational firms to reduce taxable profits. This pattern is consistent with the insights from Buettner et al. (2012), who showed that audit pressure alters corporate capital structuring practices. In Tanzania, audit presence may have led to the reduction of base erosion tactics, especially through interest deductions and service payments between related entities.

Another crucial insight relates to policy timing. While the upward trend in revenues was visible even before 2018, the steeper incline post-regulation demonstrates the role of institutional reform in enhancing enforcement capacity. This resonates with the conclusions of Olaoeye and Ekundayo (2019), who highlight the importance of statutory backing and internal capacity in sustaining tax administration gains. Recent studies emphasize the complementary role of digitalization in audit efficiency. McCluskey and Huang (2019) argue that ICT-driven audit tools, including integrated taxpayer databases and automated risk flags, significantly improve audit coverage and reduce administrative bottlenecks. In Tanzania, expanding the TRA’s digital infrastructure can enhance the audit process by enabling real-time transaction tracking and more effective taxpayer profiling.

Additionally, the behavioural dynamics of audited taxpayers must be considered. Ebrahim et al. (2021) observed that firms subject to audits often display a post-audit behavioral shift, especially when audit findings are accompanied by corrective advisory or regulatory engagement. This supports the idea of a cooperative compliance framework in which audits are not solely punitive but also serve as educational tools to guide proper tax planning. Furthermore, the sustainability of audit outcomes may depend on periodic follow-ups. As noted by Kasper and Alm (2020), the deterrent effect of audits tends to wane over time if enforcement is not sustained or visible. For Tanzania, this implies that a recurring audit cycle coupled

with continuous staff training and sector-specific audit specialization may be essential in preventing compliance fatigue.

Finally, audit success also hinges on institutional trust. Feld and Frey (2002) emphasized that when audits are perceived as fair and transparent, they are more likely to elicit voluntary compliance. In this context, TRA’s emphasis on transparency and impartiality will strengthen the social contract and increase long-term tax morale, especially among large taxpayers who often possess the capacity to contest findings legally.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study strongly indicate that transfer pricing audits implemented by the Tanzania Revenue Authority in 2018 led to significant improvements in both total tax revenue and corporate income tax. These improvements, supported by statistical evidence, reflect the effectiveness of targeted policy interventions in curbing base erosion and profit shifting among large taxpayers. The regression results underscore the value of audit reforms, not just as deterrent tools but as mechanisms for actual revenue enhancement, especially within complex intra-group financial environments.

However, the sustainability of these outcomes depends on continued investment in audit infrastructure, institutional capacity, and technological integration. As this study reveals, the impact of transfer pricing audits is not only quantitative but also behavioral. Multinational enterprises, when confronted with increased audit risk, tend to adjust their tax reporting behavior in the short term. For long-term effectiveness, these audits must be systematically implemented and supported by complementary policies such as taxpayer education, clear legal frameworks, and robust digital tracking mechanisms.

To maintain and further strengthen the gains observed, the following recommendations are proposed: (1) institutionalize regular and risk-based audits within the TRA’s operational framework; (2) scale up auditor training and cross-sector specialization; (3) integrate audit findings with legal and enforcement teams to resolve disputes efficiently; (4) invest in data analytics and ICT infrastructure for real-time monitoring of related-party transactions; and (5) enhance transparency and taxpayer engagement through cooperative compliance programs. These recommendations, if adopted, will not only improve revenue collection but also foster a culture of compliance and fairness within Tanzania’s tax ecosystem.

DECLARATIONS

Data Availability Statement

Data used in this study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author gratefully acknowledges the support and cooperation of the Large Taxpayer Department at the Tanzania Revenue Authority, whose insights and data contributions were vital to the success of this study.

FUNDING

This study was conducted without the support of external funding or sponsorship.

REFERENCES

1. Advani, A., Elming, W., & Shaw, J. (2021). *The Dynamic Effects of Tax Audits*. The Review of Economics and Statistics, 1–45.
2. Agosto, E., Manzo, M., Modica, A., & Pisani, S. (2017). *Tax Audits and Tax Compliance: Evidence from Italy*. Retrieved from: <https://www.irs.gov/pub/irs-soi/17resconmodica.pdf>
3. Alm, J., Jackson, B. R., & McKee, M. (2009). *Getting the word out: Enforcement Information Dissemination and Compliance Behavior*. Journal of Public Economics, 93(3–4), 392–402.
4. Beebeejaun, A. (2018). *The Efficiency of Transfer Pricing Rules as a Corrective Mechanism of Income Tax Avoidance*. Journal of Civil & Legal Sciences, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2169-0170.1000237>
5. Bhattacharjee, S., & Baid, K. (2018). *Tax as A Major Source of Government Funding in India*. ISSN: 2394-2770, Volume 05 Issue 4(1).
6. Buettner, T., Overesch, M., Ulrich, S., & Wamser, G. (2012). *The Impact of Thin-Capitalization Rules on the Capital Structure of Multinational Firms*. Journal of Public Economics, 96(11–12), 930–938.
7. Chalu, H., & Mzee, H. (2018). *Determinants of Tax Audit Effectiveness in Tanzania*. Managerial Auditing Journal, 33(1), 35–63. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-06-2016-1390>
8. Chatama, Y. J. (2013). *The Impact of ICT on Taxation: The Case of Large Taxpayer Department of Tanzania Revenue Authority*.
9. Ebrahim, A., Kisanga, E., Swema, E., Leyaro, V., Mhede, E.P., Mdee, E., Palviainen, H., & Pirttilä, J. (2021). *The Effects of a Risk-based Approach to Tax Examinations: Evidence from Tanzania*. WIDER Working Paper 2021/150.
10. Feld, L. P., & Frey, B. S. (2002). *Trust Breeds Trust: How Taxpayers are Treated*. SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.263351>
11. Kasper, M., & Alm, J. (2020). *Audits, Audit Effectiveness, and Post-audit Tax Compliance*. Tulane University Department of Economics. <http://repec.tulane.edu/RePEc/pdf/tul2010.pdf>
12. Lohse, T., & Riedel, N. (2012). *The Impact of Transfer Pricing Regulations on Profit Shifting*

“Impact of Transfer Pricing Audits on Revenue Collection Efficiency in Tanzania’s Large Taxpayer Department”

- within European Multinationals*. FZID Discussion Paper No.1-2012.
<https://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:bsz:100-opus-7962>
13. McCluskey, W., & Huang, C. (2019). *The Role of ICT in Property Tax Administration: Lessons from Tanzania*.
 14. Melnychenko, R., Pugachevska, K., & Kasianok, K. (2017). *Tax Control of Transfer Pricing*. Investment Management and Financial Innovations, 14(4), 40–49. [https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.14\(4\).2017.05](https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.14(4).2017.05)
 15. OECD. (2013). *Addressing Base Erosion and Profit Shifting*. Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.
 16. Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA). (2020). *Transfer Pricing Guideline*.
 17. United Nations. (2011). *An Introduction to Transfer Pricing*. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD).